

Conserving Natural Resources through Indigenous Practices in India

Dr. Gitumoni Rajbongshi

Department of Economics, Jagiroad College, Morigaon, Assam

Corresponding E-mail : gitueco23@gmail.com

India is blessed with rich flora and fauna since ancient times and is crucial in attracting tourists across the globe not just due to its varied biodiversity, but also due to rich culture and heritage. Since ancient times, protection and preservation of nature has been given utmost importance. Aboriginal people are closest to the forests as they are inseparable from the nature and its surrounding. These indigenous communities have been sustaining forests since ages, as they respect and conserve biological resources by expressing them through ancient scriptures. This paper is an attempt to discuss about the importance of the indigenous community in preserving forest covers and to discuss on the various challenges faced by them over time. The various methods used by the indigenous communities to preserve forests such as sacred groves, forest management, rotational grazing, fire lines, preserving medicinal plants, etc. have been presented in this paper. The study also discussed about the importance of traditional knowledge system in preserving forest and environment. The various ways in which the traditional knowledge can be preserved have also been discussed.

Keywords: Traditional knowledge system, Indian knowledge, indigenous communities, forests, sacred groves